

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED GWO-RBFNN FOR
THE EFFECTIVE FUNCTIONING OF RSM IN
ELECTRIC VEHICLES**

By

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the study entitled “**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED GWO-RBFNN FOR THE EFFECTIVE FUNCTIONING OF RSM IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES**” submitted by **Dr.BALAJI .V** to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by his under my supervision and guidance. The content of thereport, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the awardof any degree or diploma.

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CHAPTER 1

SYNOPSIS

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED GWO-RBFNN FOR THE EFFECTIVE FUNCTIONING OF RSM IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is regarded as the approach to design and create machines which have the ability to act independently. The technical methodologies and theoretical foundations used for designing software and hardware systems are studied with AI. These systems aid in improving the electronic computer performance which is similar to human intelligence. Data science defines the process of deriving predictive models, insights and knowledge from data. It also includes the storing, retrieving and processing of data. Considering a task, initially, an impactful question is formulated indicating whether the task is correlative or predictive. Subsequently, the variables or features are synthesized following which, the adopting of machine learning (ML) is carried out. Generally, machine learning is defined as a subset of AI and assists the software applications in providing accurate prediction results.

The machine learning algorithms are used in data science for making accurate estimations for a particular set of data. The adopting of ML technology aids in analyzing data and preparing features in relation to the issues in data preparation. The process of model training relies on both the choice of ML algorithm and the quality of the training data in which the selection of ML algorithm is based on end-user needs. Further, the training data set is partitioned into testing and training data followed by the selection of metrics for evaluating the model. In spite of training and assessing the model, the parameters of the machine learning model can be fine-

tuned which in turn generates improved outputs with better accuracy. Finally, the prediction process is carried out in which the prediction errors are minimized by the determination of better balance between the variance and bias for a successful task related to data science.

At present, electric vehicle (EV) revolution exhibits a wide spread throughout the world and various models have been revealed in the transportation market. Within next five years, EVs are expected to attain price parity with traditional combustion- engine vehicles due to the inclusion of AI. Generally, AI and machine learning contributes the rapid processing of abundant quantities of sensor data in EVs enabling the manufacturers to add updated predictive maintenance and enhance existing maintenance operations. In EV propulsion system, the motor drive system is regarded as a key element since it acts as a predominant source of power in electric vehicles. Among the various existing motors, the Reluctance Synchronous Motor (RSM) are widely used in EV due to its advantages like large starting torque, high efficiency, low weight, small size, noiseless operation and high power density. These RSM based zero- emission vehicles are powered by PV panels through storage batteries and the electric motor provides traction in vehicles. The efficient tracking of power from the PV system is mandatory which enables the generation of improved outputs. Machine Learning techniques are used for the tracking of maximum power from PV systems but the existing approaches are regarded as unstable learning models due to the presence of large training set, under fitting and over fitting problems, presence of noisy sets causing trapping on local minima solutions and lack of generalization. Added to this, a machine learning model demands rich training set leading to delicate generalization ability. Hence, this work concentrates on the adopting of an optimized machine learning classifier for the tracking of maximum power from PV system which in turn enables improved functioning of RSM in EVs.

1.2. LITERATURE SURVEY

M. Adnane et al (2021) have established a Driving Mode Predictor (DMP) which is a type of ML. This is first attempt to utilize ML to optimize energy in fully electric vehicle. A Driving Mode Predictor (DMP) automatically estimates the vehicle's

driving mode in real-time based on the vehicle's speed history to improve the Energy management Strategy (EMS). The addition of the DMP into the EMS provides upgraded EMS known as DMP-based EMS for determining the power to be draw from each of the EV's energy sources in real time based on the EV's speed history. The derived DMP has prediction accuracy of 92.84%. However, ensemble learners and feature selection are required for further accuracy improvement.

K. L. Lopez et al (2019) have proposed an intelligent charging method that employs ML techniques to determine when the Electric Vehicle have to be charged during connection sessions. The first stage in the technique is to use dynamic programming to discover the optimum solution for previous connection sessions. Using these optimal decisions as well as other historical data, Machine Learning models has been trained to make best decisions in real time. The proposed method explains how using an offline optimization method with DNN can produce a solution that is extremely near to the global optimum. Also reduces charging cost. However, to drive different charging decisions game theory have to be applied.

C. Vidal et al (2020) have made a review of battery state estimate method based on Machine Learning (ML) techniques like Support Vector Machines (SVM), Feed forward Neural Networks (FNN), Radial Basis Functions (RBF), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Hamming networks. The results shows that RBF has the largest average error of 2.2%, FNN has 0.7% of error, RNN has 0.5% error, SVM has 0.4% and FNN average error is 0.2%.However, more analysis into the computational complexity of training and implementing machine learning models is required.

L. Dostal et al (2020) have presented neural network-based ML approach. To solve the vibration load prediction issues for electric cars, it uses a hybrid combination model. For the combination of ML and ARMAX, the proposed method analyses the performance of a hybrid ML approach. A new hybrid technique based on ARMAX model and LDTM network has been proposed. The proposed method has given best prediction results. Validation, on the other hand is difficult and has to be further improved.

K. Chaudhari et al (2022) have investigated a supervised machine learning based approach to predict EV charging behaviour. This is because the charging process for an electric vehicle has been predicted based using input variables. This set of variables has been chosen because since they are more easily obtained in the real world. The Random Forest machine learning approach needs few variables while maintaining good accuracy. However, the ML based controller have to be further improved in order to optimally dispatch DERs for EV charging scenarios.

H. Tieng et al (2020) have proposed a Dynamic-Balancing-Inspection (DBI) scheme that combines pre-processing, data collection and Convolution Neural Network based models and activation function. The crucial information from frequency data is automatically extracted by the machine and delivers on-machine and real-time entire wheel balancing check. The proposed CNN based DBI method on machine has precisely correcting unbalanced weights and predicting weights/angles on time. However, the position and orientation of objects are not encoded perfectly and also needs large amount of training data.

G. Crocioni et al (2020) have compared different ML algorithms for evaluating discharging capacity of LI-Ion battery, by using Forward and Recurrent Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). A small neural network is designed for predicting the efficiency of LI-ion batteries using NASA datasets. Then pre-trained NNs has been integrated into an STM32 microcontroller for embedded applications that required little power and memory. The predictions showed that CNN GRU, which compose of recurrent layers outperforms all other networks. However, the lack of recurrent layers, increases the accuracy loss.

W. Zine et al (2018) have given a permanent magnet synchronous motor's rotor position estimator. The suggested estimator is based on a Machine Learning (ML) algorithm, which is one of the widely used approaches in artificial intelligence. Data that links phase currents and voltages to rotor position is used to build estimator model. The light fingerprint of the machine learning based estimator has been implemented in real time on a low-cost microcontroller. The cost-effective position estimator has been developed. However, during high speed, there is a shortage of ground-truth data, which has to be rectified further.

F. Aslay and N. S. Ting (2022) have proposed an artificial neural network (ANN) model to estimate the output current ripple in Electric Vehicles (EVs) battery charging approach. The inductance current ripple, load variations and switching frequency has been used to develop the proposed ML approach. The enhanced ANN system has been compared to Random Forest (RF) and Linear Regression (LR). Other strategies are outperformed by the proposed ANN model. However, in order to achieve better results, it is required to combine some optimization process along with this proposed method.

M. S. Islam (2018) have proposed a novel SOC based technique for calculating day-ahead combined probabilistic charging loads in electric vehicles. The charging strategy calculates two decision variable factors for each time slot and then broadcasts them to each individual EV. Using those criteria, the charging rate for each eV unit in terms of its own SOC has been estimated. By reducing the number of variable factors involved, the processing time and memory needs has been greatly reduced. However, the proposed technique for real-time EV charging has to be further enhanced.

1.3. RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFY

The incorporation of AI and machine learning in EVs have led to tremendous improvements in the manufacturing sector. The adopting of renewable energy source in EVs concentrate on reduced greenhouse gas emissions paving the way for clean and sustainable environment. Numerous methods using ML approaches for the tracking of maximum power from PV system are proposed in literature. Despite being simple and reliable, these approaches generate continuous power fluctuations leading to reduction in energy yield and efficiency drop. Moreover, the tracking speed is not quick enough to adapt to variations in irradiance. Another issue with existing ML approaches are long training time, computational complexity and strong dependency on training data. Moreover, existing ML approaches requires tuning of parameters for the generation of accurate and precise outputs. These factors insist the need for the introduction of an enhanced AI based machine learning approach which generates optimal and accurate outputs.

1.4. OBJECTIVES OF THE PROPOSED WORK

For mitigating all the above issues occurring in the prevailing techniques, a novel methodology is introduced and its contributions are stated below.

- To enable the effective functioning of EVs by using Radial Basis Function Neural Network (RBFNN).
- To reduce the computational complexity and time consumption.
- To generate accurate and optimal outputs with the adopting of Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) for tuning the RBFNN parameters.

1.5. METHODOLOGY TO BE FOLLOWED

The present population focus on the development of the decarbonized and sustainable transportation and energy generation system for tackling the global warming and climate changes. Therefore, AI based EVs are highly preferred for providing an effective solution to solve global warming due to its eco-friendly mode of transportation and zero carbon emission. The inclusion of AI based machine learning approach in EVs provides improved generalization capability and have initiated the generation of accurate outputs in a timely manner. The block diagram indicating the proposed work is shown in Fig1.[Complied by the Author]

Fig.1.1: Proposed Block diagram

The proposed work comprises of a PV panel which is installed on the roof of the EV and the power obtained from the PV panel is not sufficient, hence requires further enhancement. This necessitates the use of a Single-Ended Primary-Inductor Converter (SEPIC) which boosts the obtained PV voltage generating improved voltage gain with reduced switching losses. The maximum power from the PV panel is extracted by the GWO-RBFNN based MPPT approach which in turn optimizes the performance and increases the output efficiency of the overall system.

The maximum values of voltage and current obtained are applied to the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) generator which in turn generates the corresponding pulses for the converter operation. A battery storage with a bidirectional battery converter is used for the effective charging and discharging of energy by maintaining the State of Charge (SOC). The obtained DC voltage at the converter output is further converted to AC form by a three phase Voltage Source Inverter (3 ϕ VSI) which in turn powers the RSM of EV. The values of voltage, current and SOC of the EV based system are continuously monitored by sensors of Internet of Things (IOT) and stored in IOT webpage.

1.5.1. Modelling of PV System

PV system is an effective as well as promising renewable energy source and plays a major role in power generation. The major component of the PV system is the solar cell which is generally a semiconductor diode disposed to solar irradiance. The V-I characteristic equation of the PV solar system is estimated as follows: The photocurrent of the PV system is given by,

$$I_{ph} = [I_{sh} + K_i (T - T_o)] * \frac{G}{1000} \quad (1)$$

Where, I_{ph} denotes the photo current (A), I_{sh} indicates the short circuit current (A), K_i denotes the short circuit temperature coefficient, T indicates the operating temperature (K), T_o represents the reference temperature (K), G denotes the solar irradiation (W/m^2). The current output of the PV module is

$$I = N_p * I_{ph} - N_p * I_s * \left[\exp\left(\frac{V}{n * V_{th}}\right) - 1 \right] - I_p \quad (2)$$

1.5.2 Modelling of SEPIC

The SEPIC converter, which is from the family of buck-boost converter is capable of generating a voltage output, which is lesser or higher than the given voltage input without the reversal of polarity. It is mainly composed of two capacitors, two inductors along with a diode and power switch.

Stage 1 : The switch is in ON condition and the diode is reverse biased, since the polarity of the coupling capacitor $C1$ is negative. The capacitor $C1$ discharges and the inductors $L1$ and $L2$ begins charging in this stage.

Stage 2 : In this stage the diode is forward biased and begins conducting. The switch is turned OFF in this stage and both the inductors $L1$ and $L2$ discharges and its energy is transferred to the capacitor $C1$ and load respectively.

The value of voltage gain of SEPIC converter is given as,

$$\frac{V_o}{V_{pv}} = \frac{D}{1-D} \quad (3)$$

where D is the duty cycle, which is given as

$$D = \frac{V_o}{V_o + V_{pv}} \quad (4)$$

The values of inductor L_1 and L_2 is as follows,

$$L_1 = \frac{V_{pv} \times D}{\Delta i_{L_1} \times f_s} \quad (5)$$

$$L_2 = \frac{V_{pv} \times D}{\Delta i_{L_2} \times f_s} \quad (6)$$

The magnitude of the output voltage ripple is given as,

$$\Delta V_o = \Delta V_{C_2} = \frac{V_o D}{RC_2 f_s} \quad (7)$$

The equations that derive the value of capacitance C_1 is given as,

$$C_1 = \frac{V_o \times D}{R \times \Delta V_{C_1} \times f_s} \quad (8)$$

The variation of voltage in capacitor C_1 is given as,

$$\Delta V_{C_1} = \frac{V_o D}{RC_1 f_s} \quad (9)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{V_o \times D}{R \times \Delta V_o \times f_s} \quad (10)$$

The maximum power from the PV system is extracted by the GWO-RBFNN approach which is explained as follows.

1.5.3. GWO-RBFNN based MPPT Approach

AI algorithms like machine learning approaches are widely used in the extraction of maximum power from the PV systems. Among these ML approaches, RBFNN is more efficient due to its strong nonlinear mapping ability and simple structure. In RBFNN, the initial network parameters affects the accuracy of the final prediction outputs. This necessitates the inclusion of optimization approach and hence GWO is used for optimizing the parameters of RBFNN. The GWO has the advantages like fast convergence speed and fewer adjustment parameters in turn efficiently optimizes RBFNN.

1.5.3.1. RBFNN optimized with GWO

RBFNN is a type of neural network in which the values are distributed by the input units to the hidden layer in a uniform manner without the multiplication of weights. The hidden units are termed as RBF units and the transfer function of these units indicates a monotonous radial basis function. The outputs from the hidden layer are applied to the output units for adding appropriate weights to generate a vector for m outputs and is given by

$$y = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m]^T.$$

The RBF neural networks is given by,

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i \phi_i(x) \quad (11)$$

In which, k indicates the number of hidden units, w_i indicates the connection weight of each hidden unit, (x) denotes the radial basis function which is given by

$$\phi_i(x) = \exp[-\|x_i - c_i\|^2 / 2\sigma_i^2] \quad (12)$$

Here, c_i denotes the center of the i^{th} basis function in the hidden layer, $x_i = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N]^T$ denotes the input vector of the neural network, σ_i indicates the width of the i^{th} node. A measured fitness function is used in RBFNN to generate accurate results and the fitness function used in this approach is Mean Square Error (MSE) which is given by

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - T_i)^2 \quad (13)$$

Here, T denotes the target output, n represents the number of input data, Y denotes the real output.

This algorithm is the leadership order in GWO algorithm that is characterized as four clusters:

- a) Alpha (α) Dominant wolf, which makes decision-may be a male or female.
- b) Beta (β) Subordinate wolf, which aids alpha in decision making.
- c) Omega (ω) Lower ranking wolf.
- d) Delta (δ) Dominates omega and should report alpha and beta.

The hunting behavior and encircling can be modeled as follows:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{G}_p(t) - \vec{G}_p(t)| \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{G}(t + 1) = \vec{G}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \quad (15)$$

Here, the location of the prey and wolf are denoted as $GP \rightarrow$ and G respectively and the current iteration is denoted as t .

The coefficient are given as, vectors are denoted as A and C

$$\vec{A} = 2\vec{a} \cdot \vec{rand}_1 - \vec{a} \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \vec{rand}_2 \quad (17)$$

Here, the value of a decreases linearly from 2 to 0, $rand1 \rightarrow$ and $rand2 \rightarrow$ are the random vector which lies in the range $[0, 1]$.

As the dominant wolves α has more experience in hunting and predicting the position of the prey, other wolves are being guided by α ; according to the position of α , the position of other wolves gets updated. The updating behavior is expressed as,

$$\begin{cases} \vec{G}_1 = |\vec{G}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha)| \\ \vec{G}_2 = |\vec{G}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta)| \\ \vec{G}_3 = |\vec{G}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\delta)| \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{cases} \vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{G}_\alpha - \vec{G}| \\ \vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{G}_\beta - \vec{G}| \\ \vec{D}_\delta = |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{G}_\delta - \vec{G}| \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$\vec{G}(t + 1) = \frac{\vec{G}_1 + \vec{G}_2 + \vec{G}_3}{3} \quad (20)$$

The value of A lies between $[-2a, 2a]$ and if $|A| < 1$, it means that the wolves attack the prey and if $|A| > 1$, then the wolves diverge from the prey. The parameters of the RBFNN are updated with the help of GWO approach to improve the accuracy and the corresponding fitness function of GWO-RBFNN is given by,

$$F = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - T_i)^2}{n} \quad (21)$$

The steps involved in the tracking of maximum power point by GWO-RBFNN are given below

- Step 1 :** Estimate the network topology and perform encoding of initial parameters into the position vector of grey wolf individuals.
- Step 2 :** Initialize the population and find the optimal solution using GWO approach and save the α wolf's position vector in the last generation.
- Step 3 :** Perform decoding of the saved position vector optimal initial network parameters.

Step 4 : Perform the training of RBFNN network till it reaches the maximum number of training steps or precision and finally generate the optimized output.

Thus the proposed optimized machine learning approach determines the duty cycle D of the SEPIC and with this optimized output, the converters provide maximum power to the RSM of EV.

1.5.4. Battery Storage

An electrochemical device indicating a rechargeable electrical battery is used in this work. During charging, the battery performs the electrical energy conversion to chemical energy and the chemical energy conversion to electrical energy occurs during discharging. When the generated energy by the PV array exceeds the energy load demand, the additional amount of energy is stored in the battery energy storage (BES) system. In case of low working efficiency of renewable sources and grid faults, the BES provides energy to the hybrid renewable energy system (HRES).

1.5.5. Three phase VSI connected RSM

The obtained power at the DC link is converted to AC form by a 3ϕ VSI and the output power is supplied to the RSM of EV. The RSM adopts the principle of magnetic reluctance for the generation of torque and insists that specific materials are reluctant to magnetic fields. Since RSM does not demand rotor bars for operation, the resistance and heat losses are removed. It also reduces the manufacturing costs due to the absence of eddy currents and generates higher torque levels.

1.6. EXPECTED OUTCOME OF THE PROPOSED STUDY

An AI based machine learning approach using GWO-RBFNN for the efficient functioning of RSM of EVs is proposed in this work. The proposed work is simulated in Matlab and the corresponding results are obtained.

Fig. 1.2: Comparison of MPPT efficiency

Fig. 2 [Complied by the Author] indicates the comparison of MPPT efficiency of GWO-RBFNN with AI approaches like SVM, Fuzzy logic, ANN and RBFNN. The proposed GWO-RBFNN generates an improved efficiency of 98.4% when compared to other AI approaches.

Table. 1.1: Comparison of voltage gain ratio

Converters	Voltage gain ratio
Boost	1:1.5
Buck boost	1:2
Cuk	1:3
SEPIC	1:8

Table 1 represents the comparison of SEPIC with other conventional converters like Boost, Buck boost and Cuk converters. The SEPIC exhibits an improved voltage gain ratio and hence generates enhanced outputs with high boosting ability.

1.6.1 Summary

This work discusses a hybrid optimization approach for a PV-based EV charging system employing a SEPIC converter. The adopting of AI approaches in PV-based EV have attracted considerable attention since they promote sustainable transportation while addressing climate change with reduced carbon footprint. A SEPIC converter regulates and boosts the PV system output, by producing gate pulses from PWM, the GWO-RBFNN based MPPT contributes to the enhancement of the switching state of the SEPIC converter. As a result, by maintaining a steady power supply, the proposed control method is able to transcend the non-linear behavior of the PV system and provide continuous power supply to the RSM of EV with reduced computational complexity and time consumption

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CHAPTER 2

OPTIMIZATION AND INTELLIGENT TECHNIQUES FOR ELECTRICAL VEHICLE

2.1. INTRODUCTION

The need for energy has increased significantly as a result of growing population. With this increase, the use of transportation is increasing in day to day life. As an environmental awareness, Electric Vehicles (EV) are introduced, which is a replacement for gasoline-powered vehicles in the automotive industry [1]. The main cause of the change is the carbon dioxide emissions that come from vehicle ignition. Therefore, an alternative to fuel-based automobiles is needed, like EV [2]. A traditional energy source utilised to produce electricity is fossil fuels. Because of the emissions of carbon dioxide, this resource is harmful to the environment either directly or indirectly [3]. Compared to internal combustion engines (ICE), EV systems have benefits like zero vehicle emissions, a low maintenance, cost efficiency and greater safety measures [4]. Also, usage of grid tied EV system causes power shortage, voltage stability etc... Therefore, it is important to use alternative energy sources to meet both current and future energy needs. Solutions to supplant traditional energy sources like coal, oil and natural gas are being used more frequently in recent years.

The utilisation of RES supports the country's energy consumption for environmental reasons. In order to boost economic potential in the competitive energy market, RES assist with existing energy needs in some places. The utilisation of RES for the provision of electricity in small cities is rising as a result of higher environmental standards [5]. To combat energy problem and environmental degradation, it is crucial to produce renewable energy (RE), which offers flexibility to lessen the effects of RE access to the grid because RE sources exhibit exceptional features of variable and uncertainty [6].

The most sustainable forms of electricity production include solar photovoltaic systems, wind energy conversion systems and many others. When comparing other sources, solar PV systems are widely selected because of their characteristics, including their permanent structure, low maintenance costs and small size [7]. Solar energy is regarded as a clean, emission-free form of energy. The enhanced solar power generation is made possible by advancements in power electronics and PV systems [8]. The current price decline of solar PV has led to an upsurge in their installation. The efficient operation of EVs depends on their ability to be charged and discharged. The installation of PV systems is crucial to the EV charging system and is also favourable in terms of the locations [9]. PV systems have advantages like renewability and cleaning, due to their unpredictable, cyclical and transient character, renewable sources have significant problems with reliability, persistence and power quality [10]. Hence, a converter operation is essential in order to improve the voltage form PV source.

In order to maximize solar power under a variety of meteorological and panel conditions, solar PV systems commonly use DC-DC converters like, Boost, CUK, SEPIC etc., to regulate the PV energy [11]. The general representation of Solar PV for EV Charging infrastructure is illustrated in Fig.2.1[11] However, the output voltage generated by converter is not stable. The problem of creating high energy regulation controller for converter operation is getting more challenging in PV system. Therefore, choice of an appropriate controller is essential in stabilizing the output obtain from DC-DC converter.

Fig. 2.1: Structure of EV Charging Using PV System

To improve the converters effectiveness, numerous rule based techniques are established. In [12] Lipschitz Optimization (LIPO) algorithm is utilized which is a powerful global optimization method that relies on Lipschitz constant which accelerate convergence rates for issues with global smoothness. Here, the modified LIPO methodology is implemented to solve the solar system MPPT issue, which helps tracking global PV system maximum power under various partial shading conditions (PSCs). However, while it's tracking speed has improved considerably, overall performance hasn't improved much. In [13] Manta Ray Foraging Optimization approach is employed, which is a bio-inspired optimization algorithm whose behaviour mimics three Manta ray foraging properties in order to create an effective optimization norm for solving novel operational problems. This approach results in generating finest solution, but not in all locations. In [14] Improved Team Game Optimization (TGO) is a proposed, which metaheuristic population based method with the benefit of requiring no tuning parameters to reduce complexity, hinged on observed behaviours of PV system during various shading conditions, solar intensity changes and load disturbances. Anyhow, it requires change when there is changes in converter. In [15] Modified Particle-Swarm Optimization (MPSO) method is described, which improves performance and boosts the output power of PV systems in unusual circumstances within short period. However, both environmental conditions and loading states affects the fitness value. Likewise, in this article, a comparison analysis is carried out between several control approaches. From the analyses it is observed that common issues like components damage in case of high current, high part counts, switching noise and ripple etc., are there. Hence, it is necessary to design an intelligent and optimized approach to tackle the issues for better performance of converter.

2.2. REVIEW ON OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

A lot of optimization and intelligent approaches were established to control the converter operation and some techniques are frequently utilized to enhance the converter performance without any computational stress. Some of the optimized techniques are detailed as follows.

2.2.1 Chaotic Flower Pollination Algorithm

A unique method for MPPT optimization has been employed in this study. The Chaotic Flower Pollination Algorithm (C-FPA) is a proposed technique that integrates chaos maps to adjust the essential algorithm parameters in an adaptive manner. Utilizing various partial shading techniques, the efficiency of the presented variants is demonstrated. Additionally, these variations are approved for monitoring the GMPP in situations where there is a quick and dynamic change in the irradiance conditions. The schematic diagram of C-FPA is illustrated in the Fig. 2.2. Mathematically, during global pollination the FPA approach is expressed as:

$$U_i^{T+1} = U_i^T + \gamma L(\lambda)(G_* - U_i^T) \quad (1)$$

At iteration T the solution vector i is specified as U_i^T , global solution as G_* , scaling factor as γ and levy factor as $L(\lambda)$.

Fig. 2.2: Schematic Representation of C-FPA

An effectiveness of the suggested variations in contrast to the FPA in standard version is assessed using a number of statistical analyses. The important finding makes it clear that combining chaos maps with FPA increases it's FPA's reliability and consistency and provides greater tracking efficiency. Nevertheless, because to its non-linearity, poor output power efficiency, short lifespan and dependence on climatic factors such as temperature and irradiance for generating power, solar PV has drawbacks and difficulties [16].

2.2.2. Population-Based Algorithm

In order to provide a long-lasting solution for partial shading issue, this article suggests brand-new population-based dynamic reconfirmation strategies. Three successful algorithms are proposed fir attaining optimal results. The suggested algorithms efficacy is assessed using certain specifications, such as the proportion of power loss and enhancement. Additionally, a typical Total Cross Tied (TCT) connection and recent publication methods like the Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Competence Square (CS) are compared to the findings. The findings of current and voltages in a TCT connected system is expressed as:

$$I_{R_x} = \sum_{y=1}^9 I_{xy}, x = 1,2, \dots,8,9 \quad (2)$$

$$V_{array} = \sum_{x=1}^9 V_{m_x} \quad (3)$$

Here, total PV current at row x is denoted as I_{R_x} , total voltage across terminals as V_{array} and voltage at row x of the PV module as V_{m_x} . Real-time irradiation data from a specific site is consider as an input to the suggested algorithms for efficient shade distribution to show a possibility of the proposed methodologies for real time implementation. Additionally, the system's many peaks are less frequent according to the PV parameters reported. This technique involves connecting PV strings to individual converters that have the same irradiation level. Nonetheless, because it uses a lot of converter circuits, this technique is costly [17].

2.2.3. Managing Energy Storage in Real-Time Stochastic Optimization

In this exploration, a real-time domestic BES power managing strategy is suggested for a householder with a Photovoltaic hybrid system to minimise daily electricity expenses, with an emergence of advanced real-time energy management algorithm with optimizing parameters. Revised load and photovoltaic profiles obtained from rolling horizon forecasts aid in boosting the energy management algorithm's ability to make the best choices. The optimization is more effective when unknown parameters and their correlation are taken into account. Reduced solar energy loss and proper use of energy storage are made possible by the incorporation of rule-based control in practical systems. Remaining offline power management techniques for the day ahead schedule of BES persist power losses in real time due to a stochastic behaviour of solar generation and its load. To lower a daily power purchase costs, optimization has been carried out in rolling horizon utilising deep learning based on memory technique with load and solar energy forecast profile. The optimum set point for BES is updated at a set interval using stochastic dual dynamic programming approach in a multistage stochastic programme a receding horizon. Online optimization techniques, on the other hand, necessitate update intervals that may cause solar energy to be postponed and discharged without necessity in actual systems [18].

2.2.4. Implementation of Multilayer Fifth Order Generalized Integrator

A unique Human Psychology Optimization (HPO) technique is implemented as adaptive control approach to monitor Global Maximum Power Point (GMPP) employing a single phase (1ϕ) two stage grid coupled partial shading system. The Structure of MFOGI is depicted in Fig. 2.3. This technique makes use of a brand-new single input fuzzy adjusted proportional integral (PI) controller and multilayer fifth order generalised integrator (MFOGI).

Fig 2.3: Architecture of MFOGI

The HPO is established for fast GMPP tracking and a photovoltaic feed forward component is integrated to a control algorithm to establish a rapid dynamic response. A benefits of MFOGI are established by analysing it with current approaches and through testing on a created laboratory prototype. These methods call for a vast amount of data, a sizable population and an intricate iterative procedure. Therefore, it is not feasible to apply this method on a cheap microcontroller due to the high computing burden [19].

2.2.5. Multi-Objective Optimization Using RESCA

A novel approach Reformed Electric System Cascaded Analysis (RESCA) or reforming power systems cascades evaluation, is being developed for an optimization of hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES), which include the grid, wind energy conversion systems, photovoltaic systems, energy storage systems and non-intermittent sources. Ho's approach has a number of drawbacks, including isolating operation mode

single constraints optimisation, primitive system component model and single source handling and simplistic power control strategy. This method addresses the aforementioned drawbacks and a case analysis on its implementation demonstrates how straightforward and reliable the optimization technique is in addressing significant shortcomings of the currently used traditional optimization strategies. The primary tenet of LPSP optimization is that the system is designed to operate with no power loss at first. Nevertheless, to resistant the shortcomings of other optimization methods, such as low conversion rates, uncertainty surrounding a conclusive answer, localised optimal solutions that rely on the input range chosen [20].

2.2.6. Hybrid Approach for Interval Prediction of Solar Output

A hybrid ensembles technique based on a probability ship model generated for the best interval prediction of on-board solar energy. A hybrid prediction procedure is generated by conjoining a number of machine learning methods. These methods include Radial Basis Function Neural Network (RBFNN), back propagation neural network (BPNN), an Elman neural network and extreme learning machine (ELM). The ELM model is written as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \beta_i \lambda(a_i x_j + b_i) = y_j, j = 1 \dots, N \quad (4)$$

Here, a_i specifies the weight vectors of input to i th hidden layer, β_i indicates the joining of i th hidden layer with output and b_i denotes the hidden nodes bias.

Additionally, because of the ship's rolling, a power requirements of on-board PV modules exhibit considerable variability and stochastic uncertainty. It indicates that estimating maritime solar irradiance with terrestrial solar power forecasting techniques leads to major forecasting errors. Therefore, compared to a challenge of land based prediction with defined sites, the forecasting challenge for solar energy on board a ship is more challenging. This work develops a hybrid ensemble forecasting model to anticipate on-board PV power outputs while taking into account the effects of ship motions in order to resolve this challenging problem. To further increase an effectiveness of forecasting, the bootstrap method is required [21].

2.2.7 Optimal Planning Utilizing BESS-PV Systems

An optimal system management is a systematic approach for a photovoltaic power plant and storage battery. The main grid will receive photovoltaic power from this integrated system while also receiving droop based primary regulated output. An algorithm for day ahead planning schedules an energy profile for trading on the day-ahead market, which also determines a primary control reserve that an integrated solution can supply on the day under consideration. Fig.2.4 illustrated the configuration scheme of the integrated system. A conjoint formulation integration of two services is the primary contribution of this work.

Fig.2.4: Block Diagram of Configuration Scheme

Additionally, the problem is specified in accordance with present grid codes and market demands. In order to account for the frequencies signal dynamics and PV generations uncertainty. It is important to note that the issue formulation is universal; there are no assumptions about the kind of battery and it performs, or highly the resources are rated. Future efforts, however, it will need to take into account of numerous functions by using a comparable methodology, as well as non-Gaussian depictions of uncertainty and stochastic models of an electricity price [22].

2.2.8 RECKF Technique for Rooftop-PV System

For a dual stage, grid connected, multifunctional Solar PV Array (SPVA) system, a Reliable Extended Complex Kalman Filter (RECKF) oriented control has been developed. It has the ability to function in conditions involving a polluted grid,

such as uneven grid voltages and under overvoltage. When compared to single stage architecture, the double stage topology has more functioning zones. The load current sensed is given by,

$$i_L = \sum_{n=1}^M I_{pn} \sin(\omega_n t_k + \varphi_n) + v_k \quad (5)$$

Here, magnitude is indicated as I_{pn} , angular frequency as ω_n and φ_n specifies the n th harmonic component of load. Also, observation noise is represented as v_k . The PI controller gains are tuned using an enhanced Real Code Particle Swarm Optimization (RCPSO) based Meta heuristic optimization technique, which successfully controls the voltage of VSC's DC link under disturbance in network. A utility of the revised RCPSO approach in maximising system performance under changing terminal voltage. Nevertheless, in accordance with advised practise and the harmonic control standard, grid current harmonics are maintained within a permitted range. Therefore, by modifying the innovation vector and consequently, the Kalman gain, the normal algorithms are still capable of functioning to anticipate the values of the states, which reduces the filter outcome [23].

2.2.9 Pareto Optimization on Solar PV

A complex urban environment of the organisation, where atypical PV shape and installations topologies are studied, to discover partial and complete shading of PV systems. Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT) for a glass section has been taken into consideration as an essential parameter of the Pareto optimization that reduces losses in a specific region with increased output energy and without flustering the effectiveness of entire system. A solar PV energy production systems can include as many solar panels as possible by maximising install variables including tilt angle, pitching, efficiency factor, elevation angle and shading to increase energy yield. The Pareto optimization (PO) method was used to design and optimise a solar system with a nominal power generation objective for a complicated structure in a densely populated in environment. This algorithm that takes into account both full and partial shadowing of photovoltaic array in an urban situation to enhance an effective energy generated by the solar panels. However

the PV module's input data needs to be given extra consideration in the suggested method because it significantly affects an outputs [24].

2.2.10. Integration of Rooftop PV Based on ATC

Considering the optimum sequencing of power factor from rooftop PV generators, a unique hierarchical multilevel decentralised Optimal Power Flow (OPF) is employed to minimise the electricity loss in 3ϕ unbalanced large scale distribution networks. To reduce energy loss while taking into consideration operating parameters, an Analytical Target Cascading (ATC) scheme based distributed sequential coordinating technique is developed. An acceptability and correctness of a parallelized coordination approach was also created and it was compared to a sequentially coordinating model in terms of solution accuracy and computing load. The described techniques, which involve OLTC collaboration and capacitor operation in distribution lines with substantial rooftop Solar PV installation, is used to a system over a prolonged period of time. But coordinating the injection of power flow by a large number of inverters for the best system functioning is a challenging problem that necessitates an appropriate strategy. [25].

2.2.11. Hybrid ANFIS-ABC Algorithm Based MPPT

For grid tied photovoltaic systems, a unique MPPT approach has been developed. Fig. 5 illustrates a hybrid Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) and artificial bee colony (ABC) approach, which are employed to maximize a degree of membership. Thus, this regulates SEPIC premised MPPT algorithm to provide quick PV power monitoring by minimizing the RMSE using Equation 6. By generating switching signals for the inverter power switches, fuzzy logic control (FLC) improves the system performance.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(\bar{Y}_i - Y_i)^2}{N}} \quad (6)$$

Fig 2.5: Architecture of ANFIS-ABC Based MPPT

The suggested hybrid MPPT controller is unusual and it uses ABC algorithm to optimize tuning of ANFIS membership function, which has not previously been described for Photovoltaic power operations. The proposed hybrid ANFIS-ABC offer improved photovoltaic tracking efficiency, quick dynamic reactions, faster convergence and robust flexibility under various weather circumstances. Future research will focus on the extension of multilevel inverter architecture with Internet of Things (IoT) and improved MPPT advancements based on machine learning [26].

2.2.12 RFCMANN Oriented MPPT Approach

This work suggests the novel Recurrent Fuzzy Cerebellar Model Articulation Neural Network (RFCMANN) illustrated in Fig.2.6,[27] is a controller used in a single stage 3ϕ , photovoltaic system to locate grid problems. Likewise, to ensure acceptable learning precision while of covering a large input space, the input space for RFCMANN controller is additionally divided into appropriate resolutions using a decision boundary. The variable learning rate coefficients are additionally established by using discrete type Lyapunov functions in order to change learning rate values while maintaining convergence of the suggested RFCMANN controller.

$$\eta_1 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^{12} \left(\frac{\partial y(k)}{\partial w_j}\right)^2 + \varepsilon}, \eta_2 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^{12} \left(\frac{\partial y(k)}{\partial m_j}\right)^2 + \varepsilon}, \eta_3 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^{12} \left(\frac{\partial y(k)}{\partial \sigma_j}\right)^2 + \varepsilon}, \eta_4 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^{12} \left(\frac{\partial y(k)}{\partial r_j}\right)^2 + \varepsilon} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2.6: Structure of RFCMANN Controller

Here ε specifies the smallest positive numbers. It is also possible to retrieve the online learning system parameters' method. Finally, a number of instances are evaluated to determine how well the suggested RFCMANN controller performs. In addition to ensuring safe operations, for a grid tied photovoltaic (PV) system during grid faults, the presented method is capable to support reactive current. An occurrence of oscillation over maximum power point and simple to lose tracking of MPP during quick irradiance level changes are drawbacks of the proposed approach [27].

2.2.13. Grid Tied PV System Using FNNGFTSMC

In this study, a transformer-less single phase (1ϕ) PV grid connected technique for adaptive Global Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Control (GFTSMC) utilizing Fuzzy Neural Networks (FNN) has been developed. The system primarily consists of a boost chopper and a dc-ac inverter. Utilizing PV array to its full potential, the boost section tracks the maximum power point. This work uses the INC approach with adjustable step size to build an MPPT of a photovoltaic system. The DC-AC converter is controlled using an optimized Fuzzy Neural Network Global Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Control (FNNGFTSMC) approach as shown in Fig. 2.7. FNN is adopted for approximating system uncertainties as:

$$\hat{g} = w^T \xi(x) \quad (8)$$

Here connection weights of FNN is denoted as w , input layer transfer function to rule layer is represented as ξ and estimation at FNN output is specified as $\hat{g}$ with uncertainties g .

Fig 2.7: Schematic Representation of FNNGFTSMC

With the aid of a GFTSMC method, the tracking error between an H-bridge inverter's output voltage and the grid reference voltage compresses to zero in a short period of time. The system uncertainties are approximated using FNN, which improves inverter robustness. Likewise, switching strength in control law is relatively low, since system instabilities are corrected iteratively, thereby reducing chattering of the system. FNNGFTSMC achieve dependable grid-connection and are flexible to changes in the external environment, however the dynamic tracking procedure is slower [28].

2.2.14 MPPT Approach with System Identification Utilizing ARV

In this research, a novel MPPT approach for a PV system with homogeneous irradiance is presented. It is created utilizing System Identification (SI) and is termed as SI-dependent polynomial Adaptive Reference Voltage (ARV) as depicted in Fig. 2.8.[29] This technique utilizes a model with a simplistic polynomial structure to calculate the reference voltage. The black box modelling technique of photovoltaic power system wherein maximum power is monitored and is used to determine the reference voltage using a SI-based polynomial modeling. In general, polynomial design

is formulated as:

$$A(q)y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} \frac{B_i(q)}{F_i(q)} u_i(t - nk_i) + \frac{c(q)}{D(q)} e(t) \quad (9)$$

The variables from A to F is specified as q^{-1} (time shift operator). Here, $e(t)$ specifies the noise with variance λ . Also, u_i indicates the i th input, the total input as n_u and i th input delay as nk_i .

Fig 2.8.Block View of SI-Based ARV MPPT Approach

The generated nonlinear model is unaffected by the PV system's physical parameters. Additionally, the issue of Maximum power capture that occurs due to temperature change has been resolved. The resulting have therefore demonstrated that the suggested reference voltage-based MPPT approach outperforms existing methods in monitoring MPP under fluctuating atmospheric conditions. Maximum power point is obtained with minimal changes in voltage, current and power. Low-level microprocessors readily perform it because of its straightforward and affordable structure. Optimizing the polynomial model's coefficients and degree leads to the creation of a system model that is more functional [29].

2.2.15 Eliminating Harmonics Using ANN-NR Approach

The PWM methodology, which uses both Newton Raphson (NR) technique and ANN, is highlighted in this research along with an integrated algorithm. In order to lessen the undesirable decreased harmonic distortion in cascaded H Bridge multi-level inverter for solar PV systems, a hybrid ANN-NR is developed in this research. The block representation of SHE-PWM is illustrated in Fig. 2.9. To improve and lower the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), harmonics are extracted by making wise decisions about switching angles and utilizing the Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE) PWM in conjunction with the same approach. The output voltage of this approach is written by,

$$f_n(t) = A_0 + \sum_{n=1}^s (A_n \cos(n\omega t) + V_n \sin(n\omega t)) \quad (10)$$

Here, the DC component is given by A_0 , harmonics as A_n and odd harmonics as V_n .

The ANN is trained using offline computations of optimal switching angles, and the estimations it produces serve as Newton Raphson method's first guess. A 3-stage boost converter is utilized to enhance the input of inverter, which is obtained from photovoltaic system. For more efficient solar PV operations and stable output, P&O-based MPPT approach is applied. The proposed method is effective and provides extremely accurate firing angles after a few cycles, thereby increasing the ability to handle local optima values. The established SHE-PWM technique is a good fit for FACTS device and grid-connected scenarios. The discussed algorithm has shortcomings, such selection strategy for new population, complexity of finding local optima with a rough search space and low convergence [30].

Fig 2.9: Structure of SHE-PWM Based on ANN-NR

2.2.16 STPV Based on Custom Neural Network

Semitransparent Photovoltaic (STPV) technology is used in a broad range of applications to enable sunlight absorptivity for generating solar electricity with some shade, which is advantageous in warm climates. The suggested methodology analyses a Thin Film Solar Cadmium Telluride Type Module to simulate the generated power that is represented by its mathematical formula and describes the efficacy of this type of PV system. A suggested model incorporates three components such as a number of hidden layer neurons, using all information available and a linear output activation function. The developed algorithm's mathematical modelling concept is represented as,

$$h_j = 1 / [1 + \exp(-\sum_{j=0}^m W_{ij}^h * X_j)] \quad (11)$$

This reduces the difficulty of resolving the network problems. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model PV systems is implemented in real-world applications and the output power of the recommended model validated both the feasibility and power quality that PV power systems demonstrate. Only a certain amount of irradiation causes each individual thin film module to generate electricity. There has been a notable increase in the number of electrical entries employing ANN-built methodologies during the last few years. However, there have not been many applications for PV systems [31].

2.2.17 Modified PUC-5 Inverter Based on ANN Approach

The reliable performance of a 1ϕ Modified Packed U Cell five level inverter (MPUC-5) for solar application to operate consistently under a variety of irradiance conditions is achieved by the development of an artificial neural network (ANN) based controller. A converter having an equal amplitude main and auxiliary dc links is characterized as an MPUC-5. The MPUC-5's output's fundamental value also has a tendency to fluctuate. It has to be capable of generating angles, which commit to an AC voltage output with a stable core value are limited to minimal THD and exclude third order harmonics caused by variations in the voltages on dc link. The test dataset has been used after training to assess the performance of network, while training and validation datasets are engaged during training. Once the best result in the validation is obtained, the training is terminated. The training dataset's over fitting is prevented. The ability to remove harmonics is achieved by increasing switching pulses. Furthermore, the difficulty of the SHE equation enhances with the number of switching pulses [32].

2.2.18 Monitoring of PV Panel Using ANN

A unique real time tracking method that employs a modest but efficient ANN, small enough to function on a cheap device has been implemented. The solar panel degradation caused by fault situations has been detected by the described PV monitoring system. The model has been developed to forecast the power output of a solar panel which is typically functioning under a variety of shifting environmental factors. Depending on the type of information required to pass across the network, a particular network topology is chosen. The Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN) as shown in Fig.2.10 [33] .approach is highlighted as an efficient technique among the many ANN topologies.

Fig 2.10: FFNN Architecture

Heterogeneous PV panels with multiple production features are regulated by the newly introduced surveillance system. The suggested tracking system has capacity to record information online over the internet to support other crucial topographies like notification, additional training, configuration management modification and, data analysis. The expense per additional PV panel decreases as more Solar panel are added to the monitoring system. Therefore, an intelligent monitoring system is essential in the event of an alteration in weather dependent energy efficiency [33].

2.2.19. Analysis of Step-Size Using RBFC Technique

An integrated fuzzy radial basis functional regulator with different step dependence is proposed. When establishing the hybrid power point finding controller, the benefits of fuzzy and ANN are taken into consideration. The RBF is comprised of five input neurons, one output side node and nine hidden layer nodes. A variable step RBFC has been used in the hybrid MPPT controller's first stages to place the PV array's operating point close to the desired power point location. Engineering based uncertainty difficulties are solved using fuzzy logic and it provides precise solutions to challenging nonlinear issues. The PV converter is operated with good efficacy in a variety of partially shadowed conditions owing to the RBFC optimized Fuzzy controller.

Furthermore, disadvantages of IC include significant complexity when coupled with traditional P&O controller and moderate power fluctuations near to the MPP [34].

2.2.20 Estimation of Hybrid ANFIS-PSO Approach

A hybrid MPPT method developed on ANFIS-PSO to obtain quick and maximum PV power even without oscillation tracking is suggested. There is no additional sensor needed to monitor irradiance and temperature variables when employing the ANFIS-PSO based MPPT approach. The technology employed provides significant driving control to improve PV energy extraction. Fast, precise and reliable PV monitoring is attained by the suggested MPPT's performance under a variety of seasonal changes. During very erratic solar irradiance, the PV energy system operates with zero stable error and a quick PV tracking convergence speed. The following mathematical formula is related to multilayer feed forward network,

$$W_j = \mu P_j(x) * \mu Q_j(y), \overline{W}_j = \frac{w_j}{w_1+w_2}, j=1,2. \quad (12)$$

The hybrid ANFIS-PSO is more effective at tracking power generation. It has the shortest execution time for RMSE and allows free extraction of antecedent variables for appropriate training under uniform, partial shading and non-uniform situations. Nevertheless, the system's temperature changes along with fluctuations in solar radiation [35].

2.3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

A complete observation is carried out between distinctive optimization approaches and intelligent techniques for analysing the performance of converter in a system. Table 1 and 2 specifies manifold approaches along with its merits and limitations.

Table 2.1: Comparative Analysis of Optimization Approaches

SI. No.	Author/Year of Publication	Methodology	Advantages	Limitations
1.	Zeyuan Yan <i>et al</i> [2019]	Improved Brain Storming Optimization (IBSO) is utilized to establish local and global search for the entire process [36]	Increasing the accuracy in identifying the parameters of different PV modeling techniques.	Restricted and multi-objective optimization and difficult renewable energy challenges demand further IBSO enhancement.
2.	Hong Liu <i>et al</i> [2019]	A fast optimization technique for BSS day-ahead monitoring is created by fusing genetic algorithm with feasible solution space [37].	Enhances the algorithm's overall uniqueness and succeeds in efficiently exploring optimum solution.	Expense of risk penalty is larger, which suggests that the solutions has lower customer satisfaction and poorer viability.
3	Abdullah M. Shaheen <i>et al</i> [2021]	Forensic Based Investigation Algorithm (FBIA) is proposed to precisely extract electrical properties of various photovoltaic configurations [38].	Comparing with other methods, FBIA model's optimal parameters are consistent.	Depends highly on case tools.
4	M. Premkumar <i>et al</i> [2021]	Chaotic map-based Gradient Based Optimizer (GBO), is utilised to analyze the PV parameter and to increase the precision and convergence rate of GBO [39].	Achieves lower RMSE, Minimizes STD value and faster convergence.	The suggested CGBO technique is anticipated to be used for industrial optimization applications and discrete optimization in future works.

Table 2.1: (Continued)

SI. No.	Author/Year of Publication	Methodology	Advantages	Limitations
5	Sad Motahhir <i>et al</i> [2021]	ABC optimization is established to draw optimum global power from each substring [40].	Provides effectiveness and precision for determining maximum available power from the complete PV system.	The slight deviation from a typical response is deemed as a problem.
6	Chanaka Keerthisinghe <i>et al</i> [2019]	Policy Function Approximation (PFA) approach is proposed for controlling PV-storage system efficiently [41].	Computationally quick for both online and offline phases, used for a longer period without updating and yet able to provide solutions of high quality.	In real-world applications, users are not able to alter the essential parameters.
7	Pengfei Zhao <i>et al</i> [2021]	A two-tage Distributionally robust- Volt-VAR pressure optimization (DR-VVPO) model is proposed, to control voltage variation, maintain gas quality and reduce IES system operation costs along with Photovoltaic uncertainty [42].	Offers system operators a workable operation plan for assuring gas quality and voltage profile stability at lower operational cost in the period of multiple energy sources and significant renewable absorption.	Volt-VAR Optimization (VVO) is slightly impacted by gas quality management.
8	Bin Huang <i>et al</i> [2021]	A Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) based Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) technique is utilized to carry out the capacity scheduling of PV-BSS [43].	In order to increase PV-net BSS's profit, PPO agent creates safe scheduling plans.	The primary drawbacks include their poor sampling efficiency and hypersensitivity towards modification of hyper parameters including step size and learning rate.

Table 2.2: Comparative Analysis of Intelligent Approaches

References	Year	Author's	Description of the Work
[44]	2019	Nishant Kumar <i>et al.</i>	Power Normalized Kernel Least Mean Fourth (PNKLMF-NN) based approach and Learning based Hill Climbing (L-HC) MPPT approach for grid tied PV system is proposed, in which PNKLMF-NN provides enhanced results on non-linear loads and helps in reducing complexity.
[45]	2022	Sara Allahabadi <i>et al.</i>	This research introduces a new two-stage GMPPT approach that combines traditional Hill Climbing (HC) technique and ANN and intends to be precise and fast.
[46]	2020	Farkhanda Aziz <i>et al.</i>	In order to efficiently identify and categorise photovoltaic system defects, this research introduces a unique method that makes use of deep (Two-Dimension) 2-D CNN to extract feature from 2-D scalogram produced from PV system data.
[47]	2021	Arunprasad Govindharaj <i>et al.</i>	To essence maximum power from solar panel, an adaptive Chebyshev back stepping neural controller is presented.
[48]	2015	Faa-Jeng Lin <i>et al.</i>	In this study, a smart controller built on a 3ϕ grid-tied photovoltaic system's reactive and active power control during grid disturbances is developed utilizing Takagi Sugeno Kang Probabilistic Fuzzy Neural Network with Asymmetric Membership Function (TSKPFBB-AMF).
[49]	2021	Veerapandiyan Veerasamy <i>et al.</i>	In this article, a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) based Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) method is employed to determine High Impedance Fault (HIF) in a solar PV integrated system.
[50]	2017	Yang Sun <i>et al.</i>	The 1ϕ , residential photovoltaic system is proposed in this research that uses ANN and adaptive dynamic programming to regulate MPPT and integrate a solar photovoltaic array with the grid utilizing an LCL-filter-based inverter.

The following comparison graph exhibits the analysis made between different optimization and intelligent approaches in terms of efficiency, THD and tracking speed.

Fig. 2.11: Comparison of Efficiency (%)

The efficiency obtained by intelligent approaches like ABCNNC, ANFIS-ABC, ANFIS-PSO, RBFC and ANN-NR is displayed in Fig.2.11.[Complied by Author] It is noticed that, the ABCNNC approach attains the maximum efficiency in comparison with other approaches. Similarly, the ANN-NR approach attains the minimum efficiency with 93.14%.

Fig. 2.12: THD value

Fig. 2.12 [Complied by Author] demonstrates the THD comparison of intelligent approaches like HIF, ANN-NR, ANFIS-PSO and ANFIS-ABC. It if noticed that, the ANFIS-ABC approach has the minimum THD value of 2.3%, which meets the standard requirements of IEEE 519-2022. Similarly, the HIF technique attains a THD value of 14.6%, which is above the IEEE standards.

Fig 2.13. Comparison of Tracking Time (Sec)

The Tracking time comparison, performed between different optimization approaches like LIPO, C-FPA, ITGA and HPO is illustrated in Fig. 2.13, [Complied by Author] which aids in making decisions based on the system performance. From the comparison it is concluded that, the tracking time of HPO is faster when compared with other approaches. Similarly, establishment of new hybrid optimized techniques results in better tracking time than the recent approaches.

2.4. CONCLUSION

EV charging systems have been incorporating solar PV modules for several years due to factors, including continuing price reductions for Photovoltaic modules, rapid EV growth and concerns over greenhouse gas emissions. However, converter operation is essential in order to boost the PV voltage. It is necessary for a converter to maintain stabilized voltage and hence controller approach is utilized. Several Intelligent

and Optimized approaches are introduced in recent years for attaining stabilized voltage, but all those approaches face common issues like slow convergence, hardware dependence, computational stress and large training data. Therefore, it is essential to develop and hybrid optimized technique to overcome such issues. In this article, a comparison analysis is accomplished between various approaches for enhancing the performance of the system, to grab the optimal approach. The comparison graph is analysed for efficiency, THD and tracking time for various approaches and optimal solutions are obtained. Thus, the evolution of electric power is expected to move inexorably toward renewable sources of energy. Hence, by developing hybrid approaches more efficient and improved outputs for control of converter operation can be attained.

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CHAPTER 3

A BIO-INSPIRED OPTIMIZER BASED ANN CONTROLLER FOR EV CHARGING

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, EVs are replacing conventional internal combustion engine (ICE). But in reality, ICEs have a variety of shortcomings that EVs potentially help to overcome. Compared to ICEs, EVs produce very less pollutants, are more energy efficient, make less noise, and require less maintenance [1, 2]. The construction of the charging stations, the period of the charging process, and the impact of these stations on the current electrical grid are just a handful of challenges which indeed to be overcome. By using quick charging methods, the charging period is drastically decreased to only a few minutes. Such methods impose large load demand and harmful impacts on the electricity grid [3, 4]. Specifically when a significant amount of filling stations are linked to the electrical grid instantaneously, numerous issues arise, including extreme overloading, unstable power, and voltage change [5-7]. The improvement of the electrical system is one resolution for such issues, but it is expensive. Using an Energy Storage System (ESS) that serve as a barrier between the utility and the EV Charging Station (EVCS) is also a superior approach [8].

The utility grid will sense less strain with the deployment of ESS, but this is still a challenge due to the anticipated high number of EVCSs in the upcoming years.

Thus, it is necessary to use clean energy sources in EVCS to highlight the effects of EV on the atmosphere. Renewable Energy Sources (RES) are generally intermittent instead of constant. Photovoltaic (PV), wind systems and bioenergy are the most frequently employed RES for EV charging systems [9, 10]. Compared to wind energy systems, PV energy systems are easier to operate as well as more efficient.

Deployment of EVs powered by solar energy is essential for tackling environmental issues in an efficient manner. Since the PV module's voltage output is so poor, a suitable DC-DC converter needs to be employed to produce enhanced voltage level. Due to its realistic structure and flexibility for voltage enhancing functions, the Boost converter [11] is one of the commonly utilized converters for PV systems.

The substantial losses and voltage regulation across the switches make it less than optimal for applications demanding step-down voltage conversion. Using a Buck-Boost converter [12-15] enables the conversion of voltage in both step-up and step-down modes, but on the downside, the outcome has inverted polarity and the input current is interrupted. The Cuk converter has continuous input current [16] but, like the Buck-Boost converter, it also has reversed output polarity. In order to overcome these issues the IBC converter with coupled inductor is proposed here, which is more efficient with reduced switching losses.

To provide the finest optimum solutions, various Meta-heuristic algorithm optimisation methods and control approaches are mostly presented out. A number of methods, including Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) [17], Particle Swarm Algorithm (PSO) [18], Genetic Algorithmic Technique (GA) [19], and Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) [20], have been investigated to enhance the effective solution. Nevertheless, these methods offer low solution accuracy and slow convergence speed. In comparison to existing metaheuristic algorithms, the Salp Swarm Optimization method (SSO) has recently been revealed to offer a better solution in handling a number of challenging engineering problems [21]. The ANN based control method is used to enhance the performance of IHGBC converter together with SSO algorithm for tuning the hyper parameters of ANN in effective manner [22]. The PI controller is being utilized extensively in various fields.

The basic requirement for employing this controller is to adjust their parameters to achieve the desired outcome. So, it is essential to implement a technique that is simple to use, extremely accurate, and quick to determine the control parameters (K_p, K_i). This is suitable because of its uncomplicated design, which is simple to comprehend and accomplish [23-25]. The application of a suitable PI controller is considered to be essential to improve the converter's dynamic qualities for generating a reliable and regulated output. Because of its simplistic and effective design, a PI controller serves primarily to regulate the functionality of the converters in a PV system.

The contribution of this work involves grid incorporated PV based EV to reduce the harmful gas from atmosphere and conceivable power production. By the implementation of IHGBC converter, the poor output voltage of PV is enhanced. With the assistance of ANN control approach the performance of IHGBC converter is improved. The operation of 1ϕ VSI which is linked to the 1ϕ grid is controlled by a PI controller.

3.2. PROPOSED SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

In this work, a grid connected PV based EVCS is suggested as an approach to enable mobility and defensible decarbonized energy production. In addition to promoting and simplifying the adoption of EVs in rural areas, the proposed PV-based EVCS is aimed at decreasing the heavy reliance on the grid for power supply in metropolitan areas. The Fig 3.1[Complied by the Author] illustrates the schematic diagram for grid incorporated PV based EV system. An IHGBC converter specifically developed for the PV system with the goal of increasing output voltage, significantly reduce steady state error and stabilise converter output. The optimized ANN controller helps to enhance the performance of proposed converter. With the assistance of the optimised ANN controller, the converter's output fluctuations are regulated and a constant output is obtained. A single phase VSI receives the converter's strengthened output and deploys it to produce an inverted output with lower THD.

Fig.3.1: Schematic representation of proposed system

3.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODELLING

3.3.1 PV System Modelling

Several PV cells are combined in parallel and series in a PV module to achieve the required level of current or voltage. The PV cell is essentially a large-area p-n junction semiconductor diode. A basic PV cell equivalent circuit based on the single diode approach is shown in Fig 3.2.[23]

Fig 3.2.: PV equivalent circuit

The PV cell output equation is written as,

$$I_c = I_{ph} - I_0 = I_{ph} - I_{sat} \left[e^{\frac{q}{AKT_c}(V+IR_S)} - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where, the Boltzmann constant, Temperature cell, stack internal resistance and identity factor are represented by K, T_c, R_s and A respectively. PN junction reverse saturation current, photocurrent, and electron charge are referred to by these terms I_{sat}, I_{ph} and q . A PV system is able to produce the required energy by considering the combinations of panels in series and parallel. The outcome from the PV panel is significantly increased by employing an appropriate converter and in this paper, an integrated IBC converter with coupled inductor is used.

3.3.2 IHGBC Converter Modelling

The proposed IHGBC comprises the configuration of High Gain Boost converter and Conventional Cuk converter. The Fig 3.3.1[Complied by Author], illustrates the circuit diagram for IHGBC converter, which enhances the voltage gain by accompanying the benefits of both high gain boost and classical Cuk converters. With the aid of a single power switch, the IHGBC converter operates in continuous current mode, bringing minimized voltage stress on regulated switch and diodes

Fig 3.3.1: Equivalent Configuration of IHGBC Converter

The following is taken into consideration when analysing the proposed scheme DC-DC converter mode operations, capacitors (C_1, C_2, C_3) and inductors (L_1, L_2, L_3) charging and discharging.

Phase 1: $[t_1 - t_2]$

At instance when $t = t_1$, the switch (S) is ON, and the inductors (L_1, L_2 and L_3) charges and capacitor C_1 discharges via S . At the same time the inductor L_3 and the diodes (D_1 and D_2) are limiting with respect to V_{C1} and V_{C2} respectively. [Complied by Author],

Fig. 3.3.2: (a) Phase 1

Phase 2: $[t_1 - t_2]$

In this mode switch is set to *OFF* position. Currently, the voltage of capacitor V_{C2} is greater than V_{C1} . As a result, C_1 is charged and the inductors L_1, L_2 and L_3 are discharged after the specified interval of time t_2 . And the diode D_1 is still under reverse bias at this time, diode D_2 is conducts continuously. Henceforth, the voltage stress across diodes is equal to voltage across switch. [Complied by Author],

Fig. 3.3.1: (b) Phase 2

In general, the choice of input inductor for converter is made based on converter's conduction mode, amount of load current required, and desire to ensure least amount of output current ripple. As a result, input inductor L_1 and L_2 value is selected to have a low current ripple Δ_{iL} . On applying Kirchhoff's law to phase 1, the capacitor values are expressed as

$$-V_{pv} + V_{L1} + V_{L2} = 0 \Rightarrow V_{L1} + V_{L2} = V_{pv} \quad (2)$$

$$-V_{C1} + V_{L3} + V_{C3} = 0 \Rightarrow V_{L3} = -V_{C3} + V_{C1} \quad (3)$$

$$i_S + i_{L1} - i_{L2} - i_{C1} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$i_O - i_{L3} - i_{C3} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$i_{C1} = -i_{L1} - i_{L2} \quad (6)$$

$$i_{C2} = -i_O \quad (7)$$

At Phase 2, switch S in OFF state, and the capacitor C_2 and C_3 attains energy from the coil, and it is verified using loops.

$$-V_{pv} + V_{L1} + V_{L2} + V_{C1} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$V_{L1} + V_{L2} = -V_{C1} + V_{pv} \quad (9)$$

$$V_{L3} + V_{C3} = 0 \Rightarrow V_{L3} = -V_{C3} \quad (10)$$

$$V_{C1} = V_{C2} \quad (11)$$

From Figure 3.3.1(b) the capacitor current i_{C1} and i_{C2} is expressed as,

$$i_{C1} = (i_{L1} + i_{L2}) - i_{D1} = i_{D2} - i_{L3} \quad (12)$$

$$i_{C2} = i_{D1} - i_o \quad (13)$$

Fig 3.4[Complied by Author], waveform represents the continuous conduction mode operation of IHGBC converter. The operation of converter is enhanced with help optimized ANN controller, which is explained briefly forthcoming section.

Fig 3.4: Waveform for modes of operation

3.4. SALP SWARM Optimized ANN Controller

3.4.1. ANN Control Strategy

Normally, an ANN is a system including one or more hidden and neurons within every layer. As an outcome, the behavior of an ANN is exactly equivalent with the response of a realistic neural network. The feed-forward ANN, also known as the FF-ANN, is utilized in this work. The input in FF-ANN simply progresses in the forward direction. Mathematically, a particular neuron's action is described as:

$$y = Act (b + \sum_{i=1}^M x_i w_i) , \quad (14)$$

Where, the activation functions are represented by $Act(.)$, w_i , b and M , correction and bias factor, x_i is every input weights, and amount of input components correspondingly, where the input characteristics $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$. An FF-ANN layer might be constructed by combining the several neurons together into single layer. The following is able to symbolize the overall solution employed to determine the outcome of single-output multi-input FF-ANN:

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= Act \left(\sum_{j=1}^J 2w_{j1}h_j + 2b_1 \right), \text{ and} \\ h_j &= Act \left(\sum_{m=1}^M 1w_{mj}x_m + 1b_j \right), \forall j = \{1, \dots, J\}, \end{aligned} \quad 15$$

When y_1 is the outcome of the ANN, $(1w_{mj}, 2w_{j1})$ denotes the hidden and output layers' weights, J denotes the hidden layers' number, M denotes the input neurons' number, and $(1b_j, 2b_1)$ denotes the layers' corresponding biases.

Fig 3.5: Proposed ANN control approach

The Fig 3.5. [Complied by Author], illustrates the schematic representation of suggested ANN based DC link control. In this paper, the optimum switching state S_{opt} is taken into consideration as controlling method's output, whereas reference dc voltage as ($V_{dc} ref$), actual dc voltage as ($V_{dc} act$), and inductor current as i_l are selected as input characteristics of developed ANN-based control method. The 15-neuron design is selected using hyper parameters tuning approach. The ANN is trained, and biases and weights are modified, through using Bayesian Regularised Approach (BRT). BRT helps to lessen or completely replace the requirement for time-consuming cross validation because it is more reliable than conventional propagation techniques.

Output Class	0	6342 21.1%	0 0.0%	100% 0.0%
	1	825 2.7%	22834 76.1%	96.5% 3.5%
		88.5% 11.5%	100% 0.0%	97.3% 2.7%
		0	1	
		Target Class		

Fig 3.6: Confusion ANN's training matrix

In this article, the ANN is trained using 60% of the randomized input data, 20% for testing, and 20% for verification. The total confusion matrix, shown in Fig 3.6[Complied by Author], is utilised to evaluate the trained ANN's accuracy. The diagonal matrix components that show the accurate categorization of the data class, whereas other elements display the incorrect classification of the data.

Fig 3.7: Main tasks in implementing IHGBC Converter with ANN-based control Method

To estimate trained ANN performance of model under the situations, it is transferred to Simulink. In conclusion, Fig3 .7[Complied by Author], depicts the entire process of the learning-based control method, emphasizing the important phases of the test and training phases. In order to adjust the control hyper parameters of ANN controller, the SSO algorithm is implemented. The detailed description of SSO algorithm is explained as follows.

3.4.2 SSO Algorithm

Seyedali Mirjalili developed the SSO algorithm, which is employed in a variety of sectors. For instance, the SSA-based methodology appears to be capable of identifying an ideal segmentation results that increases classification performance while minimizing the amount of picked input characteristics, according to the outcomes. Moreover, it's possible to employ it to modify the hyper-parameters of machine learning models such as neural networks. The salp, an aquatic organism, and its predation behaviour served as the basis for the central concept of salp. The salps frequently create a swarm known as a salp chain and proceed to the food production that has yet to be properly explained. The population of SSA is split into two categories: Depending on their position within the network, there are leaders and followers. The chain's leader is in the front, and its members follow it. Assume that n variables must be estimated for the above model, where x represents the location of a salp and y represents the food source, which designates the swarm's intended destination in the search space. Salp updates the leader's position by

$$x_i^1 = \begin{cases} y_i + r_1 ((ub_i - lb_i)r_2 + lb_i) & r_3 \geq 0 \\ y_i - r_1 ((ub_i - lb_i)r_2 + lb_i) & r_3 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where y_i is the location of the food in the i th dimension and x_i^1 is position of the first salp in i th dimension. The i th dimension lower bound and upper bound are represented by lb_i and ub_i , respectively and the three random numbers are r_1, r_2 and r_3 .

Since it combines exploitation and exploration during the whole search process, r_1 has a prominent position among the three random integers. It is described as

$$r_1 = 2e^{-\left(\frac{4l}{L}\right)^2} \quad (17)$$

where l denotes present iteration, L denotes maximum number of iterations, and r_2, r_3 denote random values between $[0, 1]$. According to Newton's law of motion, the' positions are updated using the following equation:

$$x_i^j = \frac{1}{2}\lambda t^2 + \delta_0 t \quad (18)$$

where $j \geq 2, x_i^j$ location of j th salp in i th dimension, t is time, δ_0 is initial speed and $\lambda = \frac{\delta_{final}}{\delta_0}$, Where $\delta = \frac{x-x_0}{t}$. The previous formula can be changed into the following form by assuming that $\delta_0 = 0$ and t equals the number of iterations in an optimal control problem.

$$x_i^j = \frac{1}{2} (x_i^j + x_i^{j-1}) \quad (19)$$

where $j \geq 2$. this equation demonstrates how the subsequent salps update their position based on their own and the previous salp's positions.

The limiting equation will force certain salps to return to the boundaries if they venture outside the restricted search area:

$$x_i^j = \begin{cases} l^j & \text{if } x_i^j \leq l^j \\ u^j & \text{if } x_i^j \geq u^j \\ x_i^j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Fig 3.8: Flowchart representation of SSA

Algorithm 1 The procedure of Salp Swarm (SSA) Algorithm

```
Require: Initialize the salp population  $x_i$  ( $i = 1, 2 \dots n$ ) consider  $ub$  and  $lb$ .  
while (End condition is not satisfied)  
  Calculate the fitness of each search salp  
   $F =$  the best search solution  
  Update  $r_1$  by Equation(4)  
  for each salp ( $x_i$ )  
    if ( $i == 1$ )  
      Update the position of the leading salp by Equation(3)  
    else  
      Update the position of the followers salp by Equation(6)  
    end  
  end  
  Verify the position of salps based on the upper and lower bounds  
end  
return  $F$ 
```

Even till the end condition is satisfied, all of the changes mentioned above are carried out iteratively. It ought to be noted that the food source may occasionally change as a result of the salp chain's ability to explore and utilise the area surrounding an existing solution to discover a better one. For other terms, throughout optimisation, the salp chain has the capacity to move in the direction of the global optimal solution. The SSA's method is demonstrated in Algorithm 1, which demonstrates where it begins by beginning numerous salps with random positions, iteratively updates these positions, and then finally finds a global optimisation solution. Figure 8 depicts the SSA's flowchart. The hyper parameter of the ANN controller is fine-tuned with the aid of SSA, and it also effectively ensures the constant voltage across the DC link.

3.4.3 PI Controller

The most suitable controllers in various sectors is the PI controller. The fundamental requirement in using these controllers is to adjust their parameters to achieve the desirable outcome. So, it is necessary to employ a technique that is simple to use, highly accurate, and quick to determine these control parameters (K_p , K_i). Fig 9[25] illustrates the system model for the PI controller.

Fig 3.9: Schematic Diagram of PI controller

Equation (21), in which K_p is the proportional gain and K_i is the integral gain states the general equation of the PI controller.

$$u(t) = k_p e(t) + k_i \int e(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Equation (10) is modified to Equation (11) using the Laplace transform

$$U(s) = k_p E(s) + \frac{k_i E(s)}{s} \quad (22)$$

Equation is the expression of PI with respect to the duration constraints (22)

$$U(s) = k_p \left[1 + \frac{1}{\tau_i} \right] E(s) \quad (23)$$

Where $k_i = \frac{k_p}{\tau_i}$ and $k_p = k_d/\tau_i$

The proportional and integral terms give the error signal more stable operation and lower the model's steady-state error. When K_p and K_i values are properly tuned for a closed-loop control system, the rise time is slightly reduced and the settling time is improved. To help with controller tuning, several software-based concepts have been implemented. The proposed PI controller successfully enhance the performance of single phase VSI.

3.4.4 Modelling Of Single Phase VSI

The constant DC link voltage is converted into AC with help of single phase VSI topology is illustrated in Fig 3.10.[23]

Fig 3.10: Single Phase VSI

It is comprised of a dc voltage source; four power switches T_1, T_2, T_3 and T_4 , four diodes D_1, D_2, D_3 , and D_4 . The inverter output is linked to the grid via LC filter which minimize the harmonics and maintain the sinusoidal waveform.

3.5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An efficient hybrid optimization algorithm for PV based EV charging station using IHGBC converter is discussed in this research. In this section, the suggested control approach is verified using MATLAB platform, and the attained outcomes are presented below. Table 1 represents the parameter specification of proposed method.

Table 3.1: Parameter Specifications

Parameter	Specification
Solar PV System	
Series connected solar PV cells	36
Open Circuit Voltage	12V
Short Circuit Current	8.33A
Peak Power	10KW, 10 Panels
Integrated High Gain Boost-Cuk	
L_1, L_2, L_3	1mH
C_1, C_2	2200 μ F
C_3	470 μ F

Fig 3.11: Waveforms illustration of solar panel (a) Temperature and (b) Irradiation

A PV system functioning on renewable energy is connected to the converter in order to evaluate the integrated Boost-Cuk converter's effectiveness. The temperature remained stable at 35°C as can be seen from the waveform observation in Fig 3.11(a), [Complied by Author] and this information can be employed to estimate the level of proposed method which is tackles the intermittent nature of the PV system.

According to this, Figure 11 (b)),[Complied by Author] shows a PV system that achieves irradiation of 1000 W/Sq.m.

Fig 3.12: Waveforms illustration of solar panel (a) Voltage and (b) Current

Fig .3.13: Waveforms illustration of converter output current

The proposed converter output current waveform is demonstrated in Fig 3.13.,[Complied by Author] After 0.13 sec, the output current maintains constant value of 3.5A.

Fig 3.14: Waveforms illustration of (a) output voltage of ANN controller (b) output voltage of SS- ANN controller

Fig 3.14 demonstrates the converter output utilizing SS optimized ANN controller. From the waveform it is clear that the constant voltage of 330V is maintained at 0.05sec depicted in Figure 3.14 (a) and similarly, the SS optimized ANN controller maintains stable voltage of 340V at 0.05 sec as illustrated in Fig 3. 14 (b). The waveforms for batteries are shown in Fig 3.15,[Complied by Author] (a) demonstrates that the battery's SOC is maintained at 80%. Figure 3.15(b) indicates that the current value of 1.3A is maintained. Similarly, the Fig 3.15(c),[Complied by Author] denotes the stable voltage of 12V is maintained. The voltage and current waveforms of 1 ϕ grid is shown in Fig 3.16.),[Complied by Author] The constant grid voltage of 220V is depicted in

Fig 3.16(a),[Complied by Author] similarly the current waveform of grid becomes constant after 0.06 sec at 4A magnitude as shown in fig 3.16(b),[Complied by Author]

Fig 3.15: Waveforms illustration of Battery (a) SOC (b) Voltage (c) Current

Fig 3.16: Waveforms illustration of Grid (a) Voltage (b) Current

(a)

(b)

Fig 3.17: Waveforms illustration of (a) Real Power (b) Reactive Power

Fig. 3.17, Complied by Author] shows the waveforms that indicate the reactive and real power of the 1 ϕ grid. Real power achieves a fixed value of 830W at 0.1 seconds and zero reactive power is obtained.

Fig 3.18: THD value

The intended converter THD value of 2.12% with reduced harmonics is displayed in Fig. 3.18, [Complied by Author]

Fig 3.19: Comparison analysis of IHGBC converter with different converters

Fig 3.19, [Complied by Author] indicates the comparison analysis of IHGBC converter with various converters. From the graph observation, is it noted that, the suggested IHGBC converter generates an efficiency of 94% and voltage gain 1:8 with minimized THD value of 2.12%. The obtained outcomes show that the presented method is highly effective in contrast to other techniques.

3.6. CONCLUSION

To promote the deployment of electric vehicles as primary mode of transportation in the future, a reliable grid incorporated PV based EVCS has been designed. A PV-based EVCS is suggested in this paper with the intention of reducing carbon emissions and the objective of extending the reach of EVs even in the most underdeveloped regions. The low output voltage level is regulated through the use of IHGBC Converter, which also offers minimal power losses. Thus, the IHGBC converter

is controlled using a DC link voltage control method that is based on ANN controller. With the help of SSO algorithm, ANN controller hyper parameters are tuned optimally. A PI controller is used to regulate the performance of 1 ϕ VSI linked to the grid. The simulation outcomes demonstrate that under a range of loading circumstances, ANN-based control approach performs better. From the attained results, it is clear that the suggested method has high efficiency of 94% and lowest THD value of 2.12% with negligible harmonics.

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CHAPTER 4

RBFNN MACHINE LEARNING BASED BLDC MOTOR DRIVEN PV FED ELECTRIC VEHICLE

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Fossil fuels are the main source of energy for the power generation and transportation industry. But in recent years, climate change has increased global awareness of the negative effects of fossil fuel use. The electric car charging space has grown over the past decade. Wireless charging of electric vehicles is very useful as it prevents disassembly and reduces safety risks. The principle of dynamic wireless charging technology for electric vehicles is to shorten the wireless charging time of electric vehicles and improve the power and efficiency of wireless charging equipment, which is not only to increase power charging, but also to reduce power charging.

Increase the operating frequency, thus reducing power loss during wireless communication.

Governments and businesses are switching to clean energy and reducing environmental pollution. In this case, it would involve using electric vehicles (EVs) to use electricity for transportation and renewable energy to generate electricity. Electric vehicles replace gasoline as a clean mode of transportation with low carbon emissions and low energy consumption. As technology and batteries evolve, millions of electric vehicles will be used for integration into the transportation and electric power system.

However, the lack of sufficient charging is the biggest obstacle to the spread of electric vehicles. The popularity of electric vehicles and electrical distribution equipment has brought some problems in the distribution network. Therefore, there is a growing need to plan to charge electric vehicles appropriately and to create new conditions for the use of electricity. Advances in battery technology, growth in the automotive industry, grid automation etc. increasing the prevalence of electric vehicles

and facilitating the long-term transition to better transport. For example, the cost of battery storage, which accounts for 25 percent of electric vehicle costs, is expected to fall from \$1,000 per kilowatt-hour in 2007 to \$200 in 2021.

There are more electric cars than there were five years ago. It can now be seen on the streets around the world. New electric vehicle registrations increased by 70% between 2014 and 2015. Electric vehicles are expected to make up the majority of transportation in the next 20 years.

Electric Vehicle (EVI) is an electricity-based policy and the number of electric vehicles will reach 20 million by 2020. According to the Electric Vehicle Institute, 62 percent of vehicles in the United States will be replaced by PEVs by 2050. Store batteries to power their engines. The architecture of charging station using DC bus is shown in Fig 4.1.[5] Electric cars come in many models with different types, sizes and features. Electric cars come in many models with different types, sizes and features.

Generally, EVs use 170-230 Wh/km. Most electric cars plug into a power outlet to charge.

The number of EV models available and EVs on the road is growing rapidly due to the need for charging stations. While the number of public charging stations is currently limited, public and private funding for charging stations is growing rapidly. Currently, the most important problem for electricity generation is electricity use, due to climate change and rising fossil fuel prices.

Currently, a large part of fuel consumption is distributed in transport and a large part in transport. According to the "International Energy Outlook" report, the share of the transportation sector in the world's total energy consumption will reach 55% by 2030. Electronic vehicle control requires the support of communication standards. In some cases, data is sent from grid operators to EVs; bidirectional unicast is sometimes required to control the behaviour of certain EVs; and finally, the competition of EVs for charging stations and response stations should be done in a special way.

Many companies around the world are working to develop different batteries for electric and hybrid vehicles. However, the performance of the battery module depends on the design and how the module is discharged and charged. In this sense, battery chargers play an important role in the development of this technology. Many types of electric vehicles such as battery electric vehicles (BEV), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV) in different configurations and fuel electric vehicles (FCEV) are currently being developed as alternatives to internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles.

Fig.4.1. Charging stations architecture using DC bus

4.2. EXISTING SYSTEM

The most important problem of today's climate change and increasing fossil fuel prices is electricity consumption. Currently, a large part of the use of fuel is distributed in transport, and a large part is distributed in transport. According to the "International Energy Outlook" report, the share of the transportation sector in the world's total energy consumption will reach 55% by 2030.

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Countries like India have an increasing need for electricity due to population growth and rapid economic growth. Increasing demand for electricity and the scarcity of energy resources in the country is going to reduce the gap between energy supply and demand. Renewable energy (RE) is the opposite, to close this energy gap without using a lot of energy. Among all renewable energy sources, solar energy is the most beneficial source of electricity due to its abundance, low cost and environmental friendliness. Agriculture in India uses most of its electricity for irrigation.

Therefore, solar energy is the most important renewable energy source used to run generators in water systems. Solar photovoltaic (PV) based water systems include photovoltaic panels, high efficiency motor pump units, inverter modules and battery storage. The solar PV driven irrigation pump has many advantages because it increases reliability with lower operating and maintenance costs. Motor drives that come directly from photovoltaic arrays have problems working well under a variety of conditions.

Considering all the consequences in the state for the photovoltaic generation junction, solar power generation and water use should be done.

In two-phase topology, the DC-DC converter is used for maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control to extract maximum power from the PV array, while the DC bus is usually controlled from a three-phase voltage source inverter (VSI). .). Unlike single-phase solar PV systems, this two-phase model keeps the DC bus voltage at a constant value with better response regardless of solar radiation. In recent years, many MPPT methods have been reported to extract maximum power from solar photovoltaic arrays via DC-DC power conversion. Unlike incremental conductivity (INC) and perturbation and observation (P&O) algorithms, they are the most popular and commercial MPPT methods due to their simplicity and generality. However, the performance of this technique depends on the size of the trace; the larger the step size, the faster the response, but the larger the selected step size, the oscillations will occur regularly. Additionally, solar power systems using standard P&O systems oscillate around maximum power even under constant or slowly varying radiation. Also, when sudden changes occur, P&O-based schematics can be confused with changes in direction, leading to distortions. Similarly, the INC method cannot effectively monitor the MPP of the PV array because the slope is too low during rapid change. Therefore, to solve these problems in traditional P&O and INC methods, many proposed search algorithms have been interpreted recently, such as modified P&O, improved P&O, and improved INC. Similarly, we developed a P&O algorithm that provides better tracking than standard P&O. The neural network is a powerful tool for controlling the speed of many different variables. An estimation method based on model usage correction (MRAS) is more useful than the above method because of its ease of use. Various MRAS-based schemes have been reported in the literature, i.e. As rotor flux, as back electromotive force, as active power, as power current, as stator current and back electromotive force, etc. Here is a modified MRAS based on immediate use. There is a large literature on acceleration estimation with current electronic method to minimize the error problem in transient response. The novelty of this article is summarized as follows:

- 1) A new analytical MPPT control (AMPPTC) technique with improved monitoring is

applied to the IMD-based solar photovoltaic water pumping system. 2) AMPPTC exhibits high performance sensing and high speed operation during dynamic changes. The battery is used as backup power for the solar system. 4) Hybrid photovoltaic-battery water pump system can work in single operation and battery connection operation. Due to rapid population and economic growth, countries like India have increased their electricity demand. The demand for electricity is increasing and the decreasing electricity supply makes it possible for the country to reduce the gap between electricity supply and demand. In this current system, a method has been devised to achieve maximum power point tracking (MPPT) for a solar photovoltaic (PV) array based on driving vehicle induction (IMD) along with water use. The gate signal is designed using the Space Vector Pulse-Width Modulation (SVPWM) method of a three-phase inverter. This experimental MPPT control (AMPPTC) scheme offers the fastest and cheapest operation in IMD-based water applications. The first stage uses a boost DC-DC converter operating at the MPP to convert the PV array voltage to a higher DC-link voltage using a monitoring-less measurement method.

Fig.4.2. Block Diagram of Existing System

The second stage converts the high DC voltage to a three-phase AC voltage fed to the IMD, which uses a three-phase VSI process with a Space Vector Pulse-Width Modulation (SVPWM) scheme to optimize the use of the DC bus voltage. 4 444 2. MPPT Efficiency Block Diagram of Existing System 2. Figure 4.2 [7] shows a 55 kW solar PV array used with an analytical monitoring system for a 2.2 kW (3 hp) IM-

connected water pump. The tracking performance of this MPPT method has been tested at different insolation intensity levels (1000 and 500 W/m²). Monitoring performance for both levels is almost 100%. Measure the response of the photovoltaic cell system. The tracking performance in this case was found to be poor compared to the MPPT recommendation (especially in low sunlight). Tracking performance is further improved when MPPT is performed at two insolation levels by the non-P&O MPPT algorithm. MPPT performs worst when the system is running with the P&O algorithm that controls the MPPT. Therefore, the AMPPTC method is the best method to reach the MPP of photovoltaic arrays in different solar insolation systems, which shows the efficiency and power of its behaviour is not good.

4.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The block diagram of the proposed body is shown in Fig 4.3.[Complied by the Author] In the proposal, the solar photovoltaic system is integrated with a backup battery to provide the BLDC motor for electric car use. The output of photovoltaic systems is interactive in nature, so high-income consumers need to increase their output. In this mode, the RBFNN MPPT converter uses the MPPT algorithm and gets the maximum power from the PV system. The proposed RBFNN MPPT method generates pulses to control the output of the proposed converter. During the day, photovoltaic generate enough electricity to power an electric car's BLDC motor. But at night, when photovoltaic power is not available, battery power is used as backup power to run the BLDC motor.

Fig.4.3. Block Diagram of Proposed System

The input converter output is fed to the three phase VSI and the resulting VSI output is used for the BLDC motor. Here, the actual speed and reference speed are compared to control the speed of the BLDC motor and the error is applied to the PI controller. Speed control of BLDC motor driver is achieved by PI control technology, which reduces torque ripple and ensures no noise. Determine the counter-electromotive force, generate the corresponding pulses and feed them to the VSI switch to realize constant speed control.

4.4. RBFNN ALGORITHM

A RBFNN is an artificial neural network that uses radial basis functions as activation functions as shown in Fig 4.4 [9],RBF network in its simplest form is a three-layer feed forward neural network. The first layer corresponds to the inputs of the network, the second is a hidden layer consisting of a number of RBF non-linear activation units, and the last one corresponds to the final output of the network. Activation functions in RBFNs are conventionally implemented as Gaussian functions.

$$f(x) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j h_j(x)$$

$$h_j(x) = \exp(-\frac{(x-c_j)^2}{r_j^2})$$

where c_j is center of region

r_j is width of the receptive field

Fig.4.4. RBFNN Algorithm

RBFNN have 5 parameters for optimization:

- 1- The weights between the hidden layer and the output layer.
- 2- The activation function.
- 3- The center of activation functions.
- 4- The distribution of center of activation functions.
- 5- The number of hidden neurons.

The weighted average of the hidden and open layers is calculated using the Moore-Penrose generalized pseudo-inverse. This algorithm overcomes many of the problems in standard gradient algorithms, such as the constraints, training cost, number of times, and local minimums. Due to its short learning time and wide-ranging capabilities, it is worth the real-time investment. For pattern recognition applications, the preferred radial basis function is usually the Gaussian kernel. In general, the mean and distribution of the activation function should have similar properties to the data.

Here, the Gaussian mean and width are chosen using the Kmeans clustering algorithm. According to the general estimate, if the number of hidden neurons is large enough, the centre and distribution of the activation function is uncertain to all the right levels.

4.5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Now that our model is built, we are ready to simulate the system. To do this, go to the Simulation menu and click Start or click the "Start/Pause Simulation" button (like the "Play" button) on the model window toolbar.

Since our example is a simple model, its simulation is almost instantaneous. For most systems, however, you will be able to see the progress of the simulation by looking at the elapsed time in the box at the bottom of the model window. Double-click the block to see the output of the analog gain block over time. The simulation diagram of the proposed process using the RBFNN algorithm is shown in Fig 4.5. [Compiled by the Author] .The design of the CIO boost converter is given below and the simulation diagram of the converter circuit and solar system is shown in Fig 4.6. [Compiled by the Author]

Fig.4.5. Simulink Diagram of Proposed System

Fig.4.6: Simulink Diagram of Solar System with CIO boost converter

Fig.4.7: Simulink diagram of converter

Design parameters of the Converter circuit:

$$C_1=(22)*(e^6)F, R_L=100\text{ohms}, L_1=(1)*(e^{-3})\text{H}$$

$$C_1 \text{ internal resistance}=0.005 \text{ ohms}$$

$$L_1 \text{ internal resistance}= 0.0001 \text{ ohms}$$

$$C_2=(22)*(e^6), L_2=(1)*(e^{-3})\text{H}$$

$$L_1 \text{ internal resistance}=0.005\text{ohms}, L_2 \text{ internal resistance}= 0.0001 \text{ ohms.}$$

The analog input voltage and input current for the converter are shown in figure 4.8. [Complied by the Author]. As seen in Fig 4.9, [Complied by the Author] the input voltage of the converter is 40V and the output voltage of the converter is 400V. The output power of the converter is the energy stored in the battery as shown in Fig 4.10. The energy stored in the battery is converted into an AC signal as shown in Fig 4.11. [Complied by the Author]

The inverter drives the motor of the electric car, and the simulation waveforms of the motor current, back electromotive force, motor speed and torque are shown in Fig 4.11 and Fig 4.12. [Complied by the Author]

Fig 4.8:Simulation waveform for input voltage and current

Fig.4.9: Simulation waveform for output voltage and current

Fig 4.10: Simulation waveform for battery output voltage

Fig.4.11: Simulation waveform for inverter output voltage

Fig 4.12: Simulation waveform for motor current and back EMF

Fig 4.13: Simulation waveform for Motor Speed and Torque

4.6. CONCLUSION

This project focuses on the design of a BLDC motor photovoltaic cell with backup battery suitable for electric vehicles. By integrating battery management into the plan, uninterrupted power can be provided for BLDC operation. RBFNN based on MPPT is used to extract the maximum power from the solar photovoltaic system and then puts the output as a PWM signal from the PWM generator to convert it in the CIO converter. Also this process uses a PI controller to keep the speed of the BLDC motor running smoothly. MATLAB based simulation results evaluate the feasibility of developing a photovoltaic-based EV system.

4.7. REFERENCES

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CHAPTER 5

FUZZY CONTROLLED CUK CONVERTER FOR GRID CONNECTED EV APPLICATIONS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

Today, electrification of transportation is growing daily and is a cleaner, greener innovation in the automotive sector. The prospect of disappearing fossil fuels and global warming have made electric vehicles (EV) a viable option for the transportation sector [1]. Transport is currently responsible for nearly a quarter of global energy-related CO₂ emissions and electric vehicles are seen as a low-CO₂ option for reducing these emissions [2]. By charging EVs using a sustainable energy source, such as solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, the use of electric vehicles are potentially reduce CO₂ emissions further. With both stand-alone and grid-connected systems. In the modern period, renewable energy sources are the most practical choice for generate electricity because it satisfy the rising demand without causing any environmental risks [3-4]. PV systems are now extensively utilised in a variety of applications, which is has more benefits than the other techniques for power production. Due to a number of benefits, including less expensive maintenance and operating costs, a low output of greenhouse gases and the possibility to be energy independent, the PV systems have recently been employed as the primary source of energy to charge the batteries as well as the additional burden on the grid is also decreased by the PV charging of EVs in addition to the fuel use [5-8]. PV arrays are intermittent, so intermediate power electronics interfaces are required to charge batteries in EVs. To overcome this issues DC/DC converter is required for supplying the constant voltage [9-10].

The boost converters are used [12] to step up the voltage of PV system, but the same time it produce discontinuous in output and affects the circuit gain. In [13] the buck-boost converter is utilized to enhance the efficiency of circuit performance and it

has the ability to step up and step down the voltage, but it attains low voltage gain. The disadvantage of current ripples is present in all of the aforementioned converters, which reduces the lifespan of the converter's parts and the EV battery's life cycle. Therefore, this work employed Cuk converter because it has the capacity to produce high continuous current to the input and output. The controller is essential to control the converter. In [14] the PI controller is employed to prevent significant disruptions and noise during the operations. But, this controller has the issue to give a power quality production. The PID controller is used in [15] to minimise the oscillations, as well as the steady-state inaccuracy as well as it give quick and stable responses. Due to the fact that it might amplify input signal variations and result in instability. To overcome this issues, the proposed work utilized the Fuzzy controller for better error detection.

In this work, Cuk converter is utilized to boost the voltage from the PV system, because PV system is affected by the climate conditions so it gives low voltage to the grid. Fuzzy controller is employed to generate the constant power supply and to enhance the grid performance. The output of the proposed method is simulated by the MATLAB software. As a result, the proposed techniques achieves low harmonics when compared to the existing.

5.2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

PV system is employed to convert sunlight into electricity. The voltage and current from the PV system is given to the EV battery. The excess voltage from the PV system is fed to the Cuk converter, due to the climatic condition the generated electricity from the PV system is with low voltage. Therefore, a high gain DC-DC converter is required. Cuk converter is utilized in this work to improve the voltage from the PV system but it not stable. The block diagram is represented in Fig 5.1. [Complied by Author]

Fig 5.1 Block Diagram for the proposed work

So, the Fuzzy controller is employed to stabilize the voltage and enhance the converter performance. Then the improved voltage is sent through the PWM generator into the Cuk converter. After that the DC link voltage is fed to the single phase VSI, which has the ability to convert DC into AC, which sustain the sinusoidal output and given to the grid supply.

5.2.1. PV System

Fig 5.2[16] depicts the circuit for the solar cell model, which includes diode, photocurrent, parallel resistor as well as a series resistor. The photovoltaic current is expressed as follows using the Kirchoff's circuit principles and the PV cell circuit.

$$I_{PV} = I_{GC} - I_o \left[\exp \left[\frac{eV_d}{kFT_c} \right] - 1 \right] - \frac{V_d}{R_p} \quad (1)$$

Fig 5.2. : Equivalent circuit of PV

Solar radiation and cell temperature have the greatest effects on the photocurrent I_{GC} , which is characterised as

$$I_{GC} = [\mu_{sc}(T_c - T_r) + I_{sc}]G \quad (2)$$

Here, μ_{sc} represents the temperature coefficient, I_{sc} specifies the short circuit current.

Additionally, it indicates that the saturation current of the cell changes with its temperature given as follows,

$$I_o = I_{o\alpha} \left(\frac{T_c}{T_r}\right)^3 \exp\left[\frac{eV_g}{KF} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} - \frac{1}{T_c}\right)\right] \quad (3)$$

$$I_{o\alpha} = \frac{I_{sc}}{\exp\left(\frac{eV_{oc}}{KFT_c}\right)} \quad (4)$$

Where, $I_{o\alpha}$ denotes the reversal saturation current at a reference temperature, V_g represents the semiconductor employed in the cell's band-gap, V_{oc} shows the open circuit voltage.

5.2.2. Modelling Of Cuk Converter

Using a switching regulator termed as a Cuk converter, a constant dc supply produce a changing output voltage. Fig 5.3[17] represents the block diagram of the proposed work, which contains 2 inductors, 2 capacitors, 1 switch, 1 diode and 1 resistor.

Fig 5.3: Circuit diagram for the Cuk converter

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L_1} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = \frac{i_{L1}}{C_1} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{di_{L1}}{dt} = \frac{V_{out}}{L_2} - \frac{V_{C1}}{L_2} \quad (7)$$

Fig 5.4: Waveform of Mode of operation

A capacitance releases energy to the output in this mode and a set of equations defines as ON mode as depicted in Fig 5.4(a). [Complied by Author] The diode is forward biased and transmits power to the charge in a second functioning mode, which is attained by opening the switch (OFF state), as illustrated in Figure 4(b).

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L_1} - \frac{V_{C1}}{L_1} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = \frac{i_{L1}}{C_1} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{di_{L1}}{dt} = \frac{V_{out}}{L_2} \quad (10)$$

(a)

(b)

Fig 5.5. Modes of operation (a) ON state and (b) OFF state [17]

By combining the equation (5-10) the dynamic equation of a Cuk converter is expressed as follows,

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L_1} - \frac{V_{c'}}{L_1} \cdot (1 - u) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dv_{c'}}{dt} = \frac{i_{L1}}{C_1} \cdot (1 - u) + \frac{i_{L'}}{C_1} \cdot u \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{di_{L'}}{dt} = \frac{V_{out}}{L_2} - \frac{V_{c'}}{L_2} \cdot u \quad (13)$$

The Cuk converter is expressed by product the equations (5-7) by d and equation (7-10) by

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L_1} - \frac{V_{c'}}{L_1} \cdot (1 - d) \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{dv_{c'}}{dt} = \frac{i_{L1}}{C_1} \cdot (1 - d) + \frac{i_{L'}}{C_1} \cdot d \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{di_{L1}}{dt} = \frac{V_{out}}{L_2} - \frac{V_{c1}}{L_2} \cdot d \quad (16)$$

A previous expression accurately demonstrates that the chopper is controlled by nonlinear equations. A static gain is calculated as a function of duty cycle by:

$$V_{out} = \frac{d}{1-d} \cdot V_{in} \quad (17)$$

5.2.3. System of Fuzzy Controller

A FLC basically consists of three components. Defuzzification, rule base inference, and fuzzification are examples of these blocks. Signals for error and error change are used to model the FLC. Fig 5.6 [18], illustrates a block diagram of an FLC.

Fig 5.6.Diagram for FLC

The development of a fuzzy inference system with input and output membership functions as well as the definition of the rules are included in fuzzy logic control. The Two input membership functions are present in this system. The terms "error" and "delta error" refers to output voltage errors. The duty cycle-"output1" is the only output membership function accessible. The inputs to the fuzzy logic controller will be the error and change of error of the output voltage. These two inputs are split into five groups, including NB: Negative Big, NS: Negative Small, ZO: Zero Area, PS: Positive Small, and PB: Positive Big. Table 5.1 displays the fuzzy rule basis.

Table 5. 1 Logic rules for FLC

$e/\Delta e$	PB	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM	NB
PB	NB	NB	NM	NM	NS	NS	Z
PM	NB	NB	NM	NM	NS	Z	PS
PS	NM	NM	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM
Z	NM	NS	NS	Z	PS	PM	PM
NS	NS	NS	Z	PS	PS	PM	PM
NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PM	PM	PB
NB	Z	PS	PS	PM	PM	PB	PB

5.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This project proposed for producing uninterruptable power supply to the load by using the PV system. Cuk converter is improved the voltage from the PV system. A proposed methodology is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink, as well as the resulting output waveforms are illustrated in below. Table 5.1 illustrates the parameter specification of the proposed work. As a result, the proposed work attains low THD value and high efficiency when compared to the existing techniques.

Table 5.2: Parameter specification

Parameters	Specifications
PV panel	
Power	<i>7KW</i>
Voltage	<i>500V</i>
Number of panels	<i>14</i>
Cuk converter	
Inductors L_1, L_2	<i>4mH</i>
Capacitor C_1, C_0	<i>470μF, 1000 μF</i>
Switching frequency	<i>10KHz</i>
Rated power	<i>1000W</i>

Fig 5.7 : Temperature and irradiance of solar panel

The parameters of solar panel is illustrates in fig[Complied by Author], the temperature is constantly maintained at 35C and the irradiation is constantly maintained at 1000 (W.sq.m).

Fig 5.8. Voltage and Current waveform for Solar panel and Converter

Fig 5.9: Battery SOC, current and voltage waveform

Fig 5.9[Complied by Author] specifies the voltage and current waveform for the solar panel and converter. From the figure it is observed that the voltage and current for solar panel is constantly maintained using at 75V and 13A. Battery SOC, voltage and current waveform is represented in fig 5.10, [Complied by Author] , which is analyzed that the SOC is constantly maintained at 60%. The voltage and current is gradually maintained at 1A and 12V.

Fig 5.10: Grid Voltage and Current Waveform, Real and Reactive Power Waveform

Fig 5.11 [Complied by Author] illustrates that the voltage and current from the grid is constantly maintained at THD value is illustrated in fig 5.12, [Complied by Author], from the figure it is analyzed that the proposed Cuk. The comparison of proposed method with the existing method is illustrated in Fig5.12 [Complied by Author], from the figure it is observed that the proposed method attains high efficiency of 92% and low THD value of 1.24% when compared to the conventional technique

Fig 5.11: THD value

Fig 5.12: Comparison of (a) Efficiency and (b) THD value

Fig 5.11 [Complied by Author] illustrates that the voltage and current from the grid is constantly maintained at THD value is illustrated in fig 5.12, [Complied by Author] from the figure it is analyzed that the proposed Cuk. The comparison of proposed method with the existing method is illustrated in fig5.12, from the figure it is observed that the proposed method attains high efficiency of 92% and low THD value of 1.24% when compared to the conventional technique.

5.4. CONCLUSION

This work proposed a fuzzy controlled Cuk converter for grid connected EV applications. DC-DC Cuk converter is used to enhance the voltage from the PV system. The Constant voltage is supplied by using the Fuzzy controller. The microgrid-based charging is therefore investigated in a variety of realistic circumstances, including THD value, PV power generation and various state of charge (SOC) levels. A MATLAB simulation analyse the effectiveness of the proposed technique. As a result, this work attains low THD value and high efficiency than the conventional approaches. As a result, the proposed method achieved high efficiency of 92% and Low THD value of 1.245 when compared to the conventional approaches like Boost, buck boost.

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